

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

Our Mission

Unleashing the power of Artificial Intelligence

GenoMed4All is the EU initiative to transform the response to Haematological Diseases by seizing the power of Artificial Intelligence. The project represents a quantum leap in advanced personalised medicine, pooling genomic/ '-omics' health data through a secure and trustworthy Federated Learning platform. Our disruptive AI models, scaled up by High-Performance Computing, will boost the processing capacity of data repositories from 10 clinical sites across Europe, empowering forward-thinking research of common and rare Haematological Diseases.

An open source data hub for haematological diseases

GenoMed4All will build a large-scale distributed repository of -omics health data across Europe, including: Electronic Health Record, PET, MRI and CT, Next Generation Sequencing, Microarray, Genome-Wide Association, Copy Number Variations, DNA and RNA sequencing.

Our core principles

- ❑ Innovation – using Graph Neural Networks for distributed training of deep learning algorithms.
- ❑ Interoperability – enabling collaborative, cross-border data sharing that is standard-compliant.
- ❑ Trust – offering security and privacy by design in all data exchanges, model training and storage.
- ❑ Scalability – using containerization to build modularity and facilitate massive replicability.

What are we aiming for?

86+

Clinical repositories with genomics data connected across 15 EU countries

15%

Accuracy improvement in specific genomic markers for prognosis and treatment

80%

Increase in the adoption of open standards for -omics data per clinical site

20%

Time reduction in AI analysis and model training through Supercomputing

Our Challenges

Understanding Haematological Diseases

- ❑ Most haematological diseases have a genetic background - There are up to 450 variants (both oncological and non-oncological), resulting from abnormalities in blood cells, lymphoid organs and coagulation factors.
- ❑ They represent a growing public health challenge - Haematological malignancies account for 5% of cancers, most can cause chronic health problems and many are life-threatening conditions.
- ❑ EU repositories on genomic and clinical data are unconnected - The number of available samples for haematological disorders remains small and there are currently no centralized big data repositories.

Validating Artificial Intelligence in Haematological Diseases

GenoMed4All will deploy 'white box' AI models in 3 real-world pilots that will enhance diagnostic capacity, predict disease outcomes and treatment response, evaluate treatment alternatives and estimate drug repurposing in common and rare oncological and non-oncological haematological diseases: Myelodysplastic syndromes, Multiple Myeloma and Sicke Cell Disease.

The Team

Funded by the European Union, this initiative embodies the pan-European collaboration of 23 partners from the whole value chain, including healthcare professionals, regulatory and ethics research, academia, disruptive tech and digital service provision. GenoMed4All features 10 partners from [EuroBloodNet](#), the European Reference Network (ERN) in Rare Hematological Diseases (RHD).

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